

This document summarizes the supplementary files for this study. It explains each file's purpose and provides instructions for using the RefactoBridge tool and interpreting the results.

Refactorings Detected By RefDetect

The file *Refactorings_Detected_By_RefDetect.zip* contains the Java and Kotlin refactorings detected by RefDetect from 10 repositories. The refactorings are sorted according to the commit history. The list below outlines the 19 types of refactorings included in the accompanying JSON file:

- Class-Level Refactorings: MoveClass, RenameClass, ExtractSubClass, ExtractSuperClass, ExtractInterface, ExtractClass, MoveAndRenameClass.
- Field-Level Refactorings: PullUpField, PushDownField, MoveField, EncapsulateField, RenameField.
- Method-Level Refactorings: PullUpMethod, PushDownMethod, MoveMethod, RenameMethod, ChangeMethodParameters, InlineMethod, ExtractMethod.

Although we extract refactorings applied to both Java and Kotlin classes, this study focuses exclusively on those applied to Kotlin classes. Nevertheless, we provide the Java refactorings for completeness and potential future use.

Additionally, although our models are designed to predict class-level refactorings, method- and field-level refactorings are also included, as the history of previously applied refactorings is one of the features used during training. Therefore, we provide these refactorings in the accompanying file.

Crash-Log

Along with the refactorings detected by RefDetect, the crash log available (*crash-log.json*) provides detailed information about commits where the tool (RefDetect) encountered crashes. These typically include exceptions such as invalid ref names, index out of bounds, timeouts, null pointer errors, or unexpected casts, which occurred during analysis or parsing.

Class Level Refactorings Detected By Java-Trained Model

The file **Class-Level Refactorings_ML.zip** contains seven types of Kotlin class-level refactorings detected by RefDetect across 10 Kotlin repositories. The refactorings are sorted based on commit history. For each commit, we applied the Java-trained models to assess whether they could successfully predict the corresponding refactorings detected by RefDetect. The files include the prediction results for each detected refactoring instance. **Note: cases involving test files, merge commits, or refactorings where both classes are newly added are excluded from evaluation.** Below is an example of what you can find in these files:

```

{
  "repository": "https://github.com/android/architecture-samples.git",
  "sha1": "f01fcad4193091f41352e8575d10f7718f61240e",
  "url": "https://github.com/android/architecture-samples/commit/f01fcad4193091f41352e8575d10f7718f61240e",
  "refactorings": [
    {
      "refactoring type": "RenameClass",
      "original class": "com.example.android.architecture.blueprints.todoapp.data.source.TasksDataSource",
      "target class": "com.example.android.architecture.blueprints.todoapp.data.source.NetworkDataSource",
      "description": "RenameClass: Class TasksDataSource is Renamed to NetworkDataSource",
      "validation": "TP",
      "lang": "Kotlin",
      "ML Prediction": "Positive 0.77%"
    }
  ]
}

```

Field Descriptions in the JSON File:

- **repository:** URL of the GitHub repository where the refactoring occurred.
- **sha1:** The SHA-1 hash of the commit in which the refactoring was detected.
- **url:** Direct link to the commit on GitHub.
- **refactorings:** A list of refactorings detected in the commit. Each entry includes:
 - **refactoring type:** The type of refactoring applied (e.g., RenameClass, ExtractClass).
 - **original class:** Fully qualified name of the class before the refactoring.
 - **target class:** Fully qualified name of the class after the refactoring.
 - **description:** Textual description of the refactoring performed.
 - **validation:** Model evaluation label—e.g., TP (True Positive), FN (False Negative), NC (Not Considered). **Note:** If a refactoring is detected by RefDetect but not by the model, the label is set as FN. While such cases would typically require manual review, we treat them as true positives for RefDetect—i.e., false negatives for the model. Please refer to the paper for details on the validation methodology.
 - **lang:** Programming language of the refactored class (e.g., Kotlin or Java).
 - **ML Prediction:** Model's prediction along with its confidence score (e.g., Positive 0.77). Each prediction is accompanied by a confidence score, representing the probability that a refactoring has occurred. This score is generated by the classification model trained to detect refactorings. For instance, in the example above, the model predicts the refactoring with 77% confidence.

Excluded Cases in Model Evaluation: In our experiments, we exclude three specific cases from model evaluation. Refactorings that fall into these categories are excluded from the results, and the validation field for such instances is marked as "NC" in the JSON file.

- 1. Test Files:** In line with the original paper, Refactorings applied to test files are excluded from evaluation. This is because the prediction models were not trained on test classes, and we follow the same approach in this study. Although test files were ignored in the paper, they are included in this dataset for completeness. However, they are not considered during evaluation. **Any file with "test" in its full name or its file path that contains the word "test" is excluded.**
- 2. Merge Commits:** In line with the original paper, we evaluate only files that were changed in each commit, as determined using the `diff` command. If a merge commit introduces no conflicting changes, the `diff` command yields no output. As a result, no instance is created for metric calculation—effectively treating it as an empty commit. However, the corresponding refactorings are still detected by RefDetect in the individual (pre-merge) commits rather than in the merge commit itself. **Therefore, we exclude merge commits. In addition, any commits that do not belong to the <main> or <master> branch are excluded.**
- 3. Refactorings Involving Only New Classes:** When both the original and target classes in a refactoring are newly added, the refactoring is still logged in the dataset. However, since we rely on `diff` to extract features from the previous commit, such classes are not available in earlier versions. As a result, these refactorings are excluded from evaluation, similar to how we handle merge commits. For example, if all classes involved in a refactoring are new, the model cannot extract the necessary metrics to make a prediction. **Therefore, these cases are marked as not considered and excluded from analysis.**

Random Forest Models Used in the Study

The file `random-forest.zip` includes the trained model, scaler, and feature set used in this study. Detailed instructions on how to use these components are provided in the following section.

RefactoBridge: Metrics Extraction and Evaluation Tool

RefactorBridge is the tool we developed to perform the evaluation. Below, we provide an overview of the tool, along with instructions for setup and usage.

RefactoBridge consists of two components:

1. A Java-based tool that extracts 37 source code metrics from Kotlin projects, as listed in Table I of the paper. The tool is provided as a JAR file named **KotlinMetrics-0.0.1-SNAPSHOT.jar**, and its source code is included in the file **KotlinMetrics.zip**.
2. A Python-based tool for extracting four ownership metrics and three process metrics, as described in Table I of the paper. It is distributed as **Python-Tool-ML-Kotlin.zip**. This tool also performs the evaluation, ensuring full reproducibility of the results.

How to Set Up and Use RefactoBridge

You can find detailed instructions on how to configure and run the tool below.

1. Prerequisites

To set up and run this project locally, ensure you have the following prerequisites installed:

- **Python 3.7:** the safest tested version of Python that is compatible with the python packages used for this project.
 - On Linux, install it using:

```
sudo apt install python3.7
```
 - On Windows, install it via this link
<https://www.python.org/downloads/release/python-370/>
 - **Note:** Make sure to add Python to your system's PATH during installation. It allows you to run Python commands from the command line.
- **Jupyter:** Enables you to run Python code and experiment with the tool. You can use it through VS Code with the Jupyter extension (<https://marketplace.visualstudio.com/items?itemName=ms-toolsai.jupyter>), or install it directly from the official Jupyter website (<https://jupyter.org/install>).
- **Java 21:** Required to run the class metrics extraction tool.

2. Run the Tool

Step 1: Start the Java tool

This Java tool is responsible for extracting source code metrics, which are later used by the Python tool. The tool does **not** need to be in the same directory as the Python files. Simply navigate to the location of the JAR file and run the following command.

```
java -jar KotlinMetrics-0.0.1-SNAPSHOT.jar
```

After you run this, you will see this line, which means everything is working correctly:

Gateway Server Started

The JVM is now running and ready to accept connections. Please keep this terminal window open, as it runs the Java backend required for your tool. **Note:** This application has been tested on Linux. However, we have provided the source code so you can modify it if necessary.

- **Step 2:** Extract random-forest.zip to the tool directory. Your directory should look like this:

```
.
├── config.py
├── dbconfig.ini
├── external/
├── kotlin/
├── kotlin_repositories/
├── model.py
├── random-forest/
├── requirements.txt
├── run_kotlin.py
├── run_on_java.ipynb
└── run_on_kotlin.ipynb  <- you will be working with this
```

- **Step 3:** Navigate to your project folder

Open Command Prompt and change the directory to the folder that contains your project files (such as run_on_kotlin.ipynb, requirements.txt, etc.). For example:

```
cd C:\Users\YourUsername\Downloads\Python-Tool-ML-Kotlin
```

- **Step 4:** Create the virtual environment

```
python -m venv .venv
```

- **Step 5:** Activate the virtual environment

On Windows:

```
.venv\Scripts\activate
```

On Linux:

```
source .venv/bin/activate
```

You should now see (.venv) at the beginning of the command prompt.

- **Step 6:** Install required Python packages

With the virtual environment activated, install all necessary Python packages by running:

```
pip install -r requirements.txt
```

Wait until all packages are installed. For the first time, it takes some time.

- **Step 7: Choose Your Development Environment (VS Code or Jupyter Notebook)**

If using VS Code, open the project folder in VS Code by running the following command:

```
code .
```

If using Jupyter Notebook, to register the virtual environment for use in Jupyter, run:

```
pip install ipykernel
```

```
python -m ipykernel install --user --name=.venv --display-name "Python (.venv)"
```

```
jupyter notebook
```

This will launch Jupyter Notebook in your default web browser.

- **Step 8: Run the notebook cells**

Start running each cell one by one by clicking **Run** or pressing **Shift + Enter**. Below is an image showing the expected appearance and layout when everything is set up correctly.

